

“I Didn’t Know I Could Do That!” Customer-Owned Touch Points And Its Role In Fostering Intrinsic Motivation—A Review

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ABSTRACT

The paper explores the dynamic relationship between consumer-owned touchpoints and intrinsic motivation, which is important in improving consumer experiences within businesses. It investigates how these touchpoints, encompassing social media, websites, forums, and review platforms, influence consumers' internal drive for autonomy, competence, and relatedness. Drawing on self-determination theory, the paper highlights the significance of these touchpoints in fostering a sense of control, mastery, and purpose, thereby enhancing intrinsic motivation and driving engaged consumer interactions. By examining the multifaceted nature of intrinsic motivation, the paper elucidates its positive impact on brand loyalty, consumer engagement, and word-of-mouth advocacy. However, it also identifies potential challenges arising from information overload, decision fatigue, and privacy concerns, affecting consumer experiences and intrinsic motivation. Using IKEA as a case study, the paper illustrates the diverse impact of physical and digital touchpoints on consumers' feelings of accomplishment, creativity, convenience, and contribution to ethical values. It underscores the importance of balancing these touchpoints to cater to varied consumer needs and consistently foster positive intrinsic motivation throughout the customer journey. Ultimately, the paper underscores the intricate interplay between consumer-owned touchpoints and intrinsic motivation, offering insights for businesses to optimize these interactions and cultivate enduring consumer relationships.

KEYWORDS: Customer-owned touch points, Intrinsic motivation, Customer journey, Self-determination hypothesis (SDT), Anatomy

1. INTRODUCTION

Firms try to form a deep bond with their consumers. In order to achieve their goal, they establish consumer-owned touchpoints which play a pivotal role in the consumer journey. They use different methods to achieve their objectives, like having video tutorials and

running their social media platforms, enabling them to get a better understanding of their consumers. Some may be curious about how these things work and how those touchpoints work? How does a customer's intrinsic motivation mediate the effect of consumer satisfaction for customer-owned touchpoints? In what circumstances do customer-owned touchpoints moderate the experience of the consumer? The paper is aimed to give answers to these questions.

Intrinsic motivation is defined as engaging in an activity for its inherent satisfaction rather than for external rewards (Oudeyer & Kaplan, 2007). Consumer intrinsic motivation is an internal state that drives people to identify and buy products or services that fulfill conscious and unconscious needs or desires (Albert, 2017). The fulfillment of those needs can motivate them to make a repeat purchase or find different goods and services to better fulfill those needs. According to the self-determination hypothesis (SDT), certain conditions support individuals' feelings of independence, competence, and connection. These conditions are said to foster the highest quality motivation and engagement for activities. (Center for Self-Determination Theory, 2014a). In addition, SDT proposes that the degree to which any of these three psychological needs is unsupported or thwarted within a social context will robustly impact wellness in that setting detrimentally. To be specific to customers, autonomy, or the ability to make choices freely, is an important aspect of customer experience due to perceiving better control over purchase, meeting fundamental needs, and getting more positive outcomes. Competence is important to customers because it affects their perception of the brand and influences their decision to make a purchase or become a lifelong fan.

Therefore, customer experience professionals must possess a blend of communication and project management skills, as relatedness is crucial for fostering consumer engagement and building relationships, ultimately impacting customer satisfaction positively. When customers feel a sense of social relatedness, they are more likely to be intrinsically motivated, which means they are motivated by the enjoyment of the activity itself rather than external rewards. This intrinsic motivation can lead to greater satisfaction with the product or service being offered (Cherry, 2023). The interaction between consumers and companies mentioned above is called customer-owned touchpoints, if it is worked efficiently, it can significantly improve customers' overall satisfaction. However, there are times when waiting for service, such as, can lower consumer satisfaction.

Consumer-owned touchpoints have different names of the same meaning. For example, some may call it customer contact points. Having agencies is also one reason why consumer-owned touchpoints can be so successful.

Agency, or the ability to act independently and make choices, has been linked to satisfaction in various contexts. The concept of agency encompasses constructs such as "personal autonomy", "internal locus of control", and "design competence" (Cavazzoni et al., 2021). These constructs have been assessed through instruments like the General Self-Efficacy Scale and the Situation-Cognitive Interaction Style Locus of Control Scale. The agency has been associated with well-being and life satisfaction, as it allows individuals to exert control over their lives and pursue their goals.

In the context of education and work, independence has been positively associated with life satisfaction (Hitlin & Long, 2009). For instance, independence in decision-making and the ability to express oneself in challenging circumstances are crucial aspects of adult aging. Moreover, independence and autonomy in decision-making have been linked to increased life satisfaction and well-being.

In the context of mental health, independence has been found to predict life satisfaction among individuals with mental disorders (Bilge et al., 2020). Furthermore, research has shown that feelings of agency gain greater weight in shaping people's life satisfaction in response to a stronger emphasis on emancipative values. This suggests that fostering agency and independence can contribute to higher life satisfaction and overall well-being.

In summary, agency and independence are reasonable operationalizations of satisfaction because they allow individuals to exert control over their lives, pursue their goals, and adapt to changing circumstances. These constructs have been linked to well-being and life satisfaction in various contexts, such as education, work, mental health, and even shopping. By promoting agency and independence, individuals can experience higher levels of satisfaction and overall well-being (Ruggeri et al., 2020). When applying it to the business, it works in the same way as mentioned above—increasing consumer satisfaction and overall well-being.

2. DISCUSSION

Back to the theme that how customer-owned touchpoints are leveraged in business is the following:: Customer-owned touchpoints serve as pivotal assets for businesses, strategically leveraged to drive engagement, brand loyalty, and business growth. Companies harness these touchpoints by actively participating in conversations across social media platforms, responding to customer queries, sharing valuable content, and humanizing their brand voice. Additionally, businesses cultivate their own touchpoints such as websites, apps, and forums,

crafting personalized experiences that cater to individual preferences, offer seamless navigation, and facilitate transactions. These touchpoints become hubs for collecting customer data, enabling businesses to analyze behaviors, preferences, and trends, thus informing marketing strategies, product development, and customer service enhancements.

Moreover, companies utilize customer reviews and ratings platforms to showcase social proof, building trust and credibility among potential consumers (Emma S., 2023). The integration of these touchpoints fosters an omnichannel approach, ensuring a cohesive brand experience across various platforms and touchpoints, thereby creating a more immersive and consistent interaction for the consumer while driving business objectives.

Consumers engage with customer-owned touchpoints through multifaceted interactions that define their brand experiences. For instance, within social media ecosystems, consumers actively participate in discussions, share feedback, and amplify brand messages through likes, comments, and shares. Additionally, brand websites and applications offer personalized experiences where consumers interact by making purchases, leaving reviews, and seeking information, fostering a deeper connection. These touchpoints often leverage interactive elements like chatbots or customization tools, empowering consumers to shape their own journeys.

Furthermore, customer reviews and rating platforms showcase consumer engagement as they contribute their opinions, influencing potential buyers and establishing trust (Diane Eunice Narciso, 2023). Consumers give feedback and ask about the products through email communications. Collectively, these interactions across social media, websites, reviews, email, and other touchpoints reflect the active role consumers play in shaping their experiences and impacting brand perceptions.

2.1 POSITIVE, NEGATIVE, AND NEUTRAL IMPACTS OF CONSUMER-OWNED TOUCHPOINTS

The consumer-owned touchpoints have both a positive and a negative effect on the company, with the impact depending on their usage. Customer-owned touchpoints encompass various channels directly controlled or influenced by consumers, including social media platforms, personal websites, blogs, and forums. In those situations, users actively engage, share feedback, and shape brand perceptions. Additionally, review sites, online communities, and customer-generated content on e-commerce platforms represent customer-owned touchpoints where individuals contribute opinions, reviews, and discussions, impacting brand visibility and reputation.

Customer-owned touchpoints have a neutral impact, manifesting both advantageous and challenging facets for businesses. While these touchpoints offer direct access to consumer insights and preferences, aiding in refining products and services, they also pose challenges in managing and maintaining consistency across diverse channels. The abundance of touchpoints can overwhelm consumers, leading to information overload and decision fatigue. Moreover, ensuring data privacy and security across these touchpoints remains a significant concern for businesses. It is important to highlight the delicate balance between leveraging consumer-owned touchpoints for insights while respecting privacy boundaries and managing the complexities of multichannel engagement strategies.

2.2 HOW CONSUMER-OWNED TOUCHPOINTS INFLUENCE INTRINSIC MOTIVATION

Customer-owned touchpoints have a profound influence on intrinsic motivation by providing consumers with a sense of autonomy, mastery, and purpose in their interactions with brands. These touchpoints empower individuals to curate their experiences, allowing them to express preferences, provide feedback, and engage with content on their terms. This autonomy not only cultivates a feeling of control and ownership over their interactions but also enhances intrinsic motivation by satisfying the innate psychological need for self-determination. Additionally, customer-owned touchpoints often offer opportunities for mastery, enabling users to explore, learn, and navigate brand offerings or communities. For instance, in online forums or user groups, individuals can share knowledge, solve problems, or contribute expertise. By attending those groups, consumers foster a sense of competence and accomplishment. Moreover, when consumers see their feedback implemented or acknowledged by brands, it reinforces a sense of purpose, validating their role in shaping the brand's trajectory (Chu et al., 2022). The acknowledgment and responsiveness demonstrated by brands validate the importance of consumers' contributions, enhancing intrinsic motivation by reinforcing the sense of impact and meaning in their interactions.

In summary, customer-owned touchpoints facilitate intrinsic motivation by granting autonomy, supporting mastery, and affirming purpose. In this way, consumer-owned touchpoints foster more engaged and committed interactions between consumers and brands.

2.3 DETAILS ABOUT MOTIVATION

Motivation is a complex force that drives human behavior, and within the context of business, it plays a pivotal role in consumer decision-making processes (Bandhu et al., 2024). There are two primary forms of motivation: extrinsic and intrinsic, which shape individuals'

actions and choices. Extrinsic motivation involves external factors such as rewards, recognition, or incentives provided by external sources (Pandya, 2024b), while intrinsic motivation stems from internal desires, satisfaction, and personal fulfillment arising from the activity itself (Cherry, 2023).

In business, understanding motivation is crucial as it directly influences consumer behavior, purchase decisions, and engagement with brands (Kentrix, 2023). Extrinsic motivators, such as discounts, promotions, or rewards programs, often encourage immediate actions or transactions. However, they might not foster long-term loyalty or genuine commitment from consumers, as their loyalty might be tied solely to the incentives provided rather than an inherent interest in the brand or product.

Conversely, intrinsic motivation is vital in establishing deeper connections between consumers and brands. When individuals are intrinsically motivated, their engagement goes beyond transactional interactions, as they derive satisfaction, enjoyment, and a sense of purpose from their interactions with a brand (Pandya, 2024c). This intrinsic motivation leads to committed and passionate consumers who are more likely to become brand advocates, influencing others positively (Shahid & Paul, 2021).

2.4 POSITIVE, NEGATIVE, AND NEUTRAL IMPACTS OF INTRINSIC MOTIVATION

The positive impacts of intrinsic motivation in business are manifold. Engaged consumers driven by intrinsic motivation tend to exhibit higher levels of loyalty, spending more time interacting with brands, and are more inclined to provide valuable feedback. Moreover, such individuals are more likely to spread positive word-of-mouth, significantly impacting a brand's reputation and attracting new customers. For instance, individuals might actively engage in brand communities, sharing experiences, tips, and advocating for products or services, thus fostering a sense of belonging and shared purpose.

However, intrinsic motivation also has its potential negative effects. Excessive reliance on intrinsic motivation might lead to unrealistic expectations from consumers. When companies consistently strive to cater to intrinsic motivators, they might face challenges in meeting diverse individual desires and maintaining consistency across touchpoints, potentially leading to disappointment among consumers (Pandya, 2024).

Neutral impacts of intrinsic motivation stem from the nuanced nature of individual desires and preferences. While intrinsic motivation fuels engagement and passion, it can also result in information overload or decision fatigue for consumers, especially in environments with

abundant choices and stimuli. Additionally, ensuring privacy and security in the interactions driven by intrinsic motivation becomes crucial, considering the extensive use of customer-owned touchpoints.

2.5 EXAMPLES OF INTRINSIC MOTIVATION

Examples of intrinsic motivation in the context of customer-owned touchpoints illustrate how individuals engage with brands driven by personal satisfaction and fulfillment. Consumers might actively participate in online forums, not merely to seek information but to contribute, share knowledge, and feel a sense of accomplishment by assisting others. Similarly, consumers might generate content on social media platforms, not for external rewards, but to express themselves, showcase their experiences, and connect with like-minded individuals.

2.6 WHY INTRINSIC MOTIVATION IS RELATED TO CUSTOMER-OWNED TOUCHPOINTS.

In summary, the interplay between intrinsic motivation and customer-owned touchpoints highlights the significance of fostering genuine engagement and satisfaction among consumers. Brands that understand and harness intrinsic motivators effectively can build lasting relationships, create loyal advocates, and foster a sense of community around their products or services (McDermott, 2017). However, managing expectations, ensuring privacy, and addressing potential challenges associated with intrinsic motivation become imperative for businesses aiming to leverage these touchpoints effectively.

2.7 THE EXAMPLE OF IKEA

IKEA, a global titan in the realm of furniture and home accessories, has meticulously sculpted a consumer experience, that intertwines various touchpoints, each, leaving a distinct mark on intrinsic motivation. The core philosophy at IKEA resonates deeply with consumer involvement, evident across physical stores, digital interfaces, and customer engagement strategies. Central to this approach, is the notion of co-creation and self-assembly, inviting customers to actively participate in the assembly of their furniture. This hands-on engagement, fosters a sense of accomplishment and ownership, positively impacting intrinsic motivation, by instilling feelings of competence and mastery.

Fig 1. IKEA retail stores

(Source: <https://www.introba.com/work/projects/ikea-retail-stores>)

The physical stores of IKEA serve as immersive spaces, inviting exploration through meticulously designed room setups and interactive displays. This spatial configuration triggers inspiration and sparks creativity, positively impacting intrinsic motivation by stimulating imagination and encouraging personal expression. However the enormity and layout of IKEA's stores might overwhelm certain individuals, potentially leading to a negative impact on motivation due to choice overload or decision fatigue. The abundance of options could dilute the sense of autonomy, fostering feelings of being lost or pressured to make choices, thus negatively influencing motivation.

Fig 2. IKEA Ends Publication of Its Iconic 70-Year-Old Print Catalog (Source:

<https://www.marketing-interactive.com/ikea-says-goodbye-to-iconic-catalogue-after-70-years>)

In the digital realm, IKEA's touchpoints, including its website and augmented reality (AR) applications, extend the brand's reach and enhance the overall consumer experience. The convenience of browsing products online and utilizing AR features to virtually position furniture within one's living space positively impacts motivation by offering ease and reducing uncertainty associated with purchasing furniture. However, for consumers who derive satisfaction from tangible experiences, the reliance on digital interfaces might result in a neutral impact on motivation, lacking the sensory engagement of physically interacting with products.

The iconic IKEA catalog, once a tangible symbol of inspiration and exploration, has transitioned into a digital format. This shift, while aligning with evolving consumer preferences, alters the nostalgic and tangible experience of flipping through physical pages. The digitization may impact motivation neutrally, as it lacks the tactile and emotional engagement of the traditional catalog. While the digital format offers convenience, it may not evoke the same emotional connection for some consumers, thereby resulting in a neutral influence on motivation.

Fig 3. VR shopping at IKEA

<https://dronesplayer.com/>

IKEA's emphasis on sustainability and affordability, strikes a chord with consumers, tapping into their sense of purpose and values. The assurance that their purchases align with ethical and environmentally friendly practices positively impacts intrinsic motivation by fostering a sense of contribution to a greater cause. However, if consumers perceive these efforts as mere marketing tactics lacking substantial impact, it could lead to a negative influence on motivation, triggering feelings of skepticism or disillusionment.

In summary, IKEA's consumer-owned touchpoints have a significant influence on intrinsic motivation. The amalgamation of physical and digital experiences offers avenues for empowerment, creativity, and convenience, impact motivation in multifaceted ways. While co-creation and hands-on involvement evoke feelings of accomplishment and competence, the overwhelming choices in-store might negatively impact motivation. Similarly, while digital interfaces offer convenience, they might lack the sensory engagement that some consumers seek. Striking a delicate balance among these touchpoints, to cater to diverse consumer needs remains pivotal in fostering intrinsic motivation throughout the customer journey.

3. CONCLUSION

In summary, the paper explored how customer-owned touchpoints boost engagement and satisfaction in businesses. It explores how intrinsic motivation shapes customer experiences and how these touchpoints impact motivation levels. Specifically, it discusses the interplay between intrinsic motivation, such as autonomy, competence, and relatedness, and the various touchpoints consumers engage with, like social media, websites, and forums.

The concept of intrinsic motivation, driven by internal satisfaction rather than external rewards, influences consumers' interactions with brands. Touchpoints like social media, websites, and review platforms empower consumers, allowing them to curate their experiences, provide feedback, and shape brand perceptions. These interactions can foster feelings of autonomy, mastery, and purpose, enhancing intrinsic motivation and leading to more engaged and committed interactions.

Nevertheless, the extensive use of customer-owned touchpoints also presents challenges. Information overload, decision fatigue, and privacy concerns can impact consumers' experiences, potentially leading to negative effects on motivation. Additionally, intrinsic motivation can foster loyalty and passionate engagement, but it might also create unrealistic expectations for businesses and pose challenges in meeting diverse consumer desires.

The paper uses IKEA as an example to illustrate the impact of various touchpoints on intrinsic motivation. IKEA's physical stores, digital interfaces, and sustainability efforts influence consumers' feelings of competence, creativity, convenience, and contribution to a greater cause, affecting their intrinsic motivation levels.

In conclusion, we emphasize the intricate relationship between customer-owned touchpoints and intrinsic motivation, showcasing how understanding and leveraging these touchpoints

can significantly influence consumer engagement, satisfaction, and brand loyalty within businesses.

4. LIMITATIONS

There are some limitations of the study. To begin with, only one example of IKEA may not be representative enough to get a general conclusion. Perhaps more data needs to be collected from various companies. It is also important to set a limit on the region. For example, taking a deeper look at only at southern part of China, because consumer preference varies from region to region. Besides, religious issues should also be considered. Maybe in the future, there will be a study of consumer behavior and their motivations for Muslims for instance.

REFERENCES

1. Aichner, T., & Gruber, B. (2017). Managing Customer Touchpoints and Customer Satisfaction in B2B Mass Customization: A Case Study. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 8(3), 131–140. <https://doi.org/10.24867/ijiem-2017-3-114>
2. Albert, L. (2017). *Analytics: Key to uncovering and acting on customer motivations | Retail Dive*. www.retaildive.com. <https://www.retaildive.com/ex/mobilecommercedaily/analytics-key-to-uncovering-and-acting-on-customer-motivations>
3. Bandhu, D., Mohan, M. M., Nittala, N. A. P., Jadhav, P., Bhadauria, A., & Saxena, K. K. (2024). Theories of motivation: A comprehensive analysis of human behavior drivers. *Acta Psychologica*, 244(1), 104177. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104177>
4. Bilge, A., Bulut-Ugurlu, N., & Guler, C. (2020). Determination of Independence and Life Satisfaction Level of Individuals with Mental Disorder. *Florence Nightingale Journal of Nursing*, 28(2), 124–132. <https://doi.org/10.5152/fnfn.2020.19073>
5. Čaić, M., Avelino, J., Mahr, D., Odekerken-Schröder, G., & Bernardino, A. (2019). Robotic Versus Human Coaches for Active Aging: An Automated Social Presence

- Perspective. *International Journal of Social Robotics*, 12(4), 867–882.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12369-018-0507-2>
6. Cavazzoni, F., Fiorini, A., & Veronese, G. (2021). How Do We Assess How Agentic We Are? A Literature Review of Existing Instruments to Evaluate and Measure Individuals' Agency. *Social Indicators Research*, 159, 1125–1153.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-021-02791-8>
7. Center for Self-Determination Theory. (2014a). *Self-Determination Theory*.
Selfdeterminationtheory.org; Center for Self-Determination Theory.
<https://selfdeterminationtheory.org/theory/>
8. Center for Self-Determination Theory. (2014b). *Theory*. Selfdeterminationtheory.org.
<https://selfdeterminationtheory.org/theory/>
9. Cherry, K. (2023a). *Understanding Intrinsic Motivation*. Verywell Mind.
<https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-intrinsic-motivation-2795385>
10. Cherry, K. (2023b, December 13). *Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation: What's the Difference?* Verywell Mind.
<https://www.verywellmind.com/differences-between-extrinsic-and-intrinsic-motivation-2795384>
11. Chu, S.-C., Kim, H., & Kim, Y. (2022). When brands get real: The role of authenticity and electronic word-of-mouth in shaping consumer response to brands taking a stand. *International Journal of Advertising*, 42(6), 1–28.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/02650487.2022.2138057>
12. Diane Eunice Narciso. (2023, July 19). *The Power of Reviews and Customer Testimonials* | Debutify Reviews. Debutify.
<https://debutify.com/blog/reviews-and-testimonials-best-practices/>

13. Emma S. (2023, December 1). *B2B Sales and the Power of Social Proof: From Doubt to Delight*. Wwww.b2brocket.ai.
<https://www.b2brocket.ai/blog-posts/b2b-sales-and-the-power-of-social-proof>
14. Gao, W., & Fan, H. (2021). Omni-Channel Customer Experience (In)Consistency and Service Success: A Study Based on Polynomial Regression Analysis. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 16(6), 1997–2013. MDPI.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/jtaer16060112>
15. Hitlin, S., & Long, C. (2009). Agency as a Sociological Variable: A Preliminary Model of Individuals, Situations, and the Life Course. *Sociology Compass*, 3(1), 137–160. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1751-9020.2008.00189.x>
16. Kentrix. (2023, June 17). *What is Motivation in Consumer Behaviour: A Comprehensive Guide*. Kentrix.
<https://kentrix.in/what-is-motivation-in-consumer-behaviour-a-comprehensive-guide/#:~:text=Motivation%20is%20a%20fundamental%20aspect>
17. McDermott, M. (2017). *Community building: Empowering brands through the strength of unity*. Major Digital.
<https://majordigital.com/articles/community-building-empowering-brands-through-the-strength-of-unity>
18. Oudeyer, P.-Y., & Kaplan, F. (2007). What Is Intrinsic motivation? a Typology of Computational Approaches. *Frontiers in Neurorobotics*, 1(6).
<https://doi.org/10.3389/neuro.12.006.2007>
19. Pandya, J. D. (2024a). Intrinsic & extrinsic motivation & its impact on organizational performance at Rajkot city: A review. *Journal of Management Research and Analysis*, 11(1), 46–53. <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.jmra.2024.009>

20. Pandya, J. D. (2024b). Intrinsic & extrinsic motivation & its impact on organizational performance at Rajkot city: A review. *Journal of Management Research and Analysis*, *11*(1), 46–53. <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.jmra.2024.009>
21. Pandya, J. D. (2024c). Intrinsic & extrinsic motivation & its impact on organizational performance at Rajkot city: A review. *Journal of Management Research and Analysis*, *11*(1), 46–53. <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.jmra.2024.009>
22. Ruggeri, K., Garcia-Garzon, E., Maguire, Á., Matz, S., & Huppert, F. A. (2020). Well-being is more than happiness and life satisfaction: A multidimensional analysis of 21 countries. *Health and Quality of Life Outcomes*, *18*(192). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12955-020-01423-y>
23. Shahid, S., & Paul, J. (2021). Intrinsic motivation of luxury consumers in an emerging market. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, *61*(1), 102531. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2021.102531>
24. Singh, R. (2016). The Impact of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivators on Employee Engagement in Information Organizations. *Journal of Education for Library and Information Science Online*, *57*(2), 197–206. <https://doi.org/10.12783/issn.2328-2967/57/2/11>
25. Wertenbroch, K., Schrift, R. Y., Alba, J. W., Barasch, A., Bhattacharjee, A., Giesler, M., Knobe, J., Lehmann, D. R., Matz, S., Nave, G., Parker, J. R., Puntoni, S., Zheng, Y., & Zwebner, Y. (2020). Autonomy in consumer choice. *Marketing Letters*, *31*(4), 429–439. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11002-020-09521-z>
26. Yakhlef, A., & Nordin, F. (2020). Effects of firm presence in customer-owned touch points: A self-determination perspective. *Journal of Business Research*, *130*(6), 473–481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.12.044>